

A Study on the Politics and Empowerment of Weaker Sections through Grampanchayths

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Abstract

An Attempt is made in this paper is to analyse the politics, empowerment of weaker sections through Grampanchayaths Grama Panchayats are most powerful foundation of decentralized government at the village level and constitute the lowest tier of the reformed and re-institutionalized Panchayat Raj System. The 73rd amendment of Indian constitution provided 1/3rd of all seats of Panchayath raj system for weaker sections (SC's, ST's, OBC and women's). It has envisioned people's participation in the process of planning, decision – making, implementation of delivery system. This paper deals with political party affiliation the role of cast, money and muscle power in the elections of weaker section representatives in Grampanchayaths. The data was purposefully collected in a study conducted at 2017. Around 300 elected representatives of weaker sections from various Grampanchayaths of Mysore Taluk, Mysore rural district of Karnataka.

Keywords: Politics, Weaker Sections and Empowerment

Introduction

Local self governments existed in one form or another since antiquity. Panchayath Raj System was introduced in rural India, at least initially as instrument of economic and social development, the so-called community development programmes. Experience has shown however that in the existing unequal socioeconomic system upper-caste and upper-class people all along managed to monopolize higher positions in the system and that these positions were used and misused depending upon the situation for self-enhancement, So much so, for a long time Panchayath Raj System became a mere puppet in the hands of the dominant caste in rural India. Working of this system had been plagued, among other things, by the penetration of party politics and Panchayath members were divided and subdivided almost along political party-lines. Caste and class inequalities only added to this. Political rivalries, corruption, nepotism, violence and gross misuse of government funds meant to be used for improving the conditions of the downtrodden have been confirmed by the increasing body of evidence brought out by studies. This has become a matter of serious concern of enlightened leadership but also made them rethink about the whole experimentation of democratic decentralization. In India steps have been initiated to increase the participation of the

weaker sections of society in new arrangements brought into being by means of decentralized local decision-making and provision of reservation.

In Indian society the weaker sections have been oppressed through centuries on account of an inequalities and rigid social order. Their upliftment involves a multi-faceted planned process of socio-economic transformation. This has been sought to be achieved through an overall policy of protective discrimination. This policy consists of legislative and administrative measures, designed to benefit weaker sections in terms of education, employment, financial assistance, political representation and protection against exploitation.

Who are the Weaker Sections

The term 'weaker Section' has been defined differently by different authorities. The study group on the welfare of weaker sections was of the view that "we should not be wrong if the agriculture labourers, petty cultivators and village artisans also constitute weaker sections". In general the people who are economically, socially, educationally, religiously and politically backward constitute the weaker sections of the society.

The people of the weaker sections are those who are subject to both social and economic disabilities and are denied the opportunities to equip themselves to participate in administrative, political, social and cultural affairs. Weaker sections consist of vulnerable group of society needing special care and protection. They are the alienated section of the society. The weaker sections in generally consists of four main divisions: 1) The scheduled castes 2) The scheduled tribes 3) The other background classes and 4) The Women

The first two groups are listed in the constitution while the other two groups are unlisted and loosely defined, it is the least homogeneous.

1. The Scheduled Castes (SC's)

The Scheduled castes occupy the bottom most rung to the social ladder. It comprises the bulk of "Untouchables" or "untouchable castes". These castes have been discriminated by the superior castes through the ages and they have never had any kind of social acceptance from the majority of the people who belong to the upper castes. They are distributed throughout India. These groups are occupying the lowest position in social, economic and political field. This condition continues even now though lots of measures have been taken to make them equal with others.

The Simon commission first coined the expression of 'scheduled castes' and embodied it in The Government of India Act 1935. The constitution of India provided certain essential rights and benefits to scheduled castes. Article 46 promotes educational and economic Interest of SC's. Article 330 reserves representation for SC's in the Houses of the people. Article 341 empowers the president to specify the castes, races or tribes seemed as scheduled castes in a particular state or union territory. The scheduled castes in Indian society represents the weakest group in the socio economic structure whose sufferings, miseries and disabilities can be traced back to thousands of years, when the social institutions of 'varnashrama' and 'Caste' were created.

2. The Scheduled tribes

The scheduled tribes constitute the other group of the weaker sections that come under "unprivileged section" of Indian society. The tribal people who are regarded as the earliest among the present inhabitants of India have survived here with their unchanging ways of life for centuries. Many of them are still in a primitive stage and are far from the impact of modern civilization. The scheduled tribes are facing geographic separation problems, economic problems cultural problems, social problems, political problems and many other various problems in Indian society.

After the independence the tribals were recognized as the weaker sections of Indian society and the government adopted planned programmes for their upliftment. some of the measures include

abolition of untouchability, creation of tribal areas and tribal development blocks, legislation's to check their exploitation and reservation of jobs in government and Panchayath Raj institutions.

3. The other backward classes

Other backward classes constitute around more than 50% of the total population and the larger group of the weaker sections in Indian society. Defining other backward classes is not an easy job. A caste or community may be socially, economically and politically backward but even then it may be difficult to classify it under other backward classes category. The term 'backwardness' is not defined as a definite term in the Indian constitution. It is a relative term and exhaustive enough to include social, educational, economical and cultural factors. The state has the authority to classify a community or a caste under backward classes. Article 340 of Indian constitution provides provision for the appointment of a commission to investigate the conditions of backward classes. Accordingly the Indian government has appointed 'kakasahed Kalekar' commission (1953) and B.P mandal commission (1979). These two commissions follow some criteria to determine the backward castes in Indian society.

Historical Background of Grama Panchayaths

Grama Panchayath or the Gram sabha is a foundation of the Panchayath Raj System. Panchayath Raj means democratic decentralization and modernization. It falls within the great tradition of our country. We often talk about Panch Parameshwar. It means that the god speaks through the Panch. Panch Parameshwara can never be prejudicial to everybody. It is how we understand about the Grama Panchayath. Our tradition of Gram Panchayaths is elaborately manifested in our long ages. Grampanchayath's are very old in Indian society. Its structure varied from time to time. There were panchayaths in ancient and medieval periods. During the last phase of midlevel India the gram panchayaths became oblivious or ineffective. During the British period an effort was made to revive the Panchayath raj. When popular ministries were formed under The Indian Government Act-1919, various provinces passed the village Panchayath acts in 1919. After independence the Indian constitution provided great strength to Panchayath raj. So gramapanchayaths of Panchayath raj institutions became stronger and powerful. The directive principles of state policy lays down that the state shall take steps to organize gramapanchayath to enable them to function as units of self government.

73rd Amendment of Indian Constitution

The 73rd amendment aims of deepening democracy at the grass roots by making mandatory the establishment of local governance structures at different levels in rural India. It specifically identifies Panchayaths as Institutions of local self governance. It provides a constitutional status for PRI and also attempt to make them more representative. This is done by creating spaces from the weaker sections, politically or through positive discrimination. Some of the important features of the 73rd amendment is enumerated below.

Structure of PRI

1. PRI's have a Uniform three tier-structure with panchayats at the village, Intermediate and district levels, except that the middle level is not mandatory in states with a population of less than twenty lakhs.
2. Direct election of members at all levels.

Representation and Reservation

1. Reservation of seats for scheduled castes & scheduled tribes in proportion to their population.
2. One –third of all seats reserved for women.
3. For both of the above rotation among constituencies is permissible.
4. Reservation of the offices of chairpersons at all levels for the scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and women on the same lines as reservation of seats, but with mandatory rotation among constituencies.
5. Reservation for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes coterminous with the period specified in article 334 with no time limit in the case of women.

States are Permitted to Provide for the Following

1. Reservation of seats and offices of chair persons in favor of the backward class of citizens.
2. Representation of chair persons of village Panchayaths at the intermediate level and chair persons of the latter at the district level.
3. Representation of members of the lower house of parliament and the state legislatures at the intermediate and district levels.
4. Representation of members of the upper house of parliament and state legislatures at the intermediate and district levels subject to their being registered electors at the appropriate level.
5. direct elections to offices of chairpersons at the Panchayath level

Panchayath Raj in Karnataka

Panchayath Raj movement started in pursuance of Balwanth rai Mehta's Committee report of 1957. The Committee gave the blue-print of a three-tier Panchayath Raj System, which was to be introduced in all the states and union territories of the Indian Union suited to local conditions. Panchayath Raj would bring democracy to the doors of the rural people, and would evoke people's participation in the decision-making and implementing programmes and schemes.

Panchayath raj system was introduced in Karnataka state with the passing of the Mysore village Panchayath and local board act 1959. It was formally inaugurated after the completion of the first Panchayath raj elections by Dr. Rajendra Prasad, the president of India on 21st December 1960. According to this act the entire state was brought under the uniform pattern of Panchayath raj substitution. It is a three-tier structure, namely 1) Village Panchayath 2) Taluka Panchayath 3) District development council.

Karnataka's modern Panchayath raj legislation was first crafted by the janatha government of Ramakrishna hedge in 1983. A major landmark achievement of this government was to legislate the Karnataka zilla Panchayath, Taluk Panchayath samitis, Mandal Panchayath and Nyaya Panchayath act 1983. This act was substituted by a new legislation in 1993 due to 73rd amendment of Indian constitution, which is the Karnataka Panchayath raj act 1993.

Karnataka Panchayath Raj Act – 1993

The Karnataka Panchayath raj Act – 1993 divided the Panchayath raj system into a three-tier structure-zilla Panchayath at district level, Taluk Panchayath at taluk level and Grama Panchayath at village level. This act provides 33% reservation for women and for SC's and ST's in proportion to their population; it also provides 33% reservation for other backward classes which is an enabling provision under the 73rd constitutional amendment. This act provided some special benefits to weaker section in Karnataka such as.

1. Reservation of seats in favour of SC's and ST's in proportion of their population subject to minimum of 15 to 30% respective in all levels.
2. Reservation of 1/3 of seats for women at all levels
3. Reservation of 1/3 of seats to persons belonging to other backward classes.
4. Reservation of 1/3 of seats in each category (SC's, ST's and OBC and General) at all levels for women.

Politics of Empowerment of Weaker Sections

The Politics of empowerment of weaker sections deals with election, voting behaviour, political party affiliation, the role of caste, money and muscle power in the elections of gram panchayaths. Elections to Grama Panchayaths. The elections to the local government bodies have been the first and foremost point of attack by the casteist groups. From the very first election under the new system, the rights of the lower castes to participate in the democratic process and hold positions were questioned by the upper castes. Elections occupy a prominent place in the scheme of things connected with village Panchayath system. Lot of things have been said and written on the behaviour of people during elections. Over the years people have been repeatedly exposed to the process of elections and they no longer take this as a passion which people use to do during the time following independence. Many studies have revealed that among other things, caste, money, muscle-power, play a vital role in the election process and this phenomena has been described as 'Politicization of caste' and 'Criminalization of politics'. Elections have been accompanied by lot of violence and caste conflicts. Expectedly the analysis of factors in the election process does not reveal any surprises; it only goes to confirm what is widely believed. This is the popular assumption. In the present study, there is a slight twist to these notions. 75% of men of Gram Panchayats of Mysore Taluk think that caste is an important factor even though only one fourth of women members think so. With regard to money same percent think so; 'community service' was mentioned by three fourth of men and one fourth of women. Political party affiliation and support is another thing frequently mentioned both by men and women members of the Gram Panchayath. Another factor obviously is reservation of seat for women and weaker sections which determine chances of perseverance of the candidates in elections.

Voting behaviour

Voting behaviour is defined as the part of total social behaviour that revolves around the decisions that a voter makes regarding which party candidate to vote, it's not as simple as it appears to be. Lot of things seem to influence the voter in situations in which a number of political parties are engaged in cut-throat competition to capture power. It is the same story at all levels of political system-local, regional, state and national except the players are different and the modus operandi varies. It is matter of common experience that factors like money, muscle power, caste, religion and a host of other primordial particularistic factors are alleged to play a decisive role in determining the chances of success of a candidate in elections.

Factors Determining the Chances of Win in Elections

Factors	Male		Female		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Money	14	7.6	14	12.6	28	9.33
Caste	43	23.3	14	12.6	57	19
Personality of the candidate	19	10.3	7	6.3	26	8.66
Community service	12	6.52	4	3.4	16	5.33
Political parties support	18	9.7	13	11.2	31	10.33
Reservation	86	46.3	75	64.65	161	53.66
Total	184	180	116	100	300	100

It can be seen from the above Table that both men and women who took part in the survey mentioned 'reservation of seats' more number of times. 53.66 percent in case of the former and 46.30 percent in case of the latter. The same thing holds true of 'caste' though less frequently mentioned by same women. It is indeed gratifying to note that secular factors like, 'personality of the candidate', 'involvement in the community service' have been mentioned same number of times. 'Money' has been mentioned same percent of times by both the sex of the sample. Overall it may be inferred that 'reservation of seats' for weaker sections emerged as an important factor in so far as it enables the members from these sections to secure a place for them in Grama Panchayath. Securing a place is one thing and being able to use that position effectively to secure benefits and services to the people of these groups is entirely another thing. As things stand today, lack of experience, lack of economic resources, lack of what is known as 'cultural capital' till now the monopoly of upper castes and upper classes have been rendering the elected representatives of these weaker sections ineffective. It would take long time before political decentralization in the form of Grama Panchayath usher in 'social democracy'.

Conclusion

Empowerment of weaker sections, though a desirable thing is hardly achieved completely in the existing socioeconomic legal system. The Grama Panchayath system which, theoretically and practically helps in the distribution of political power which had been till now concentrated in the hands of rich people has to go a long way. It is one thing to talk of distribution, it is entirely another thing to talk of how exactly people who have the power exercise that power. The latter, depends, among other things the knowledge, experience and resources that the players are able to bring to bear upon their positions. Another thing the study shows is that notwithstanding the inherent limitations the elected members have shown lot of zeal for serving the cause of the weaker section. How far the elected representatives can really usher in social democracy in village situation time alone will give the answer. Evidence shows that there is a long way to go before the empowerment of weaker sections is achieved.

References

1. Adisheshaiah, 1964. Social background and role preference of village Pradhans, Institute of Social Sciences, New Delhi.
2. Ananthpur Kripa, 2004. Interfaces in local governance-A study in Karnataka. Madras Institute of Development Studies, Chennai.
3. Ashok.v., 2008.problems and prospects of empowerment of the weaker sections; the role of representatives of weaker sections in gram Panchayaths in rural Karnataka-(PhD thesis) Dept. of Sociology, Bangalore University, Bangalore.
4. Basu, D.D., 2001. Introduction to the Constitution of India, Macmillan, Delhi.
5. Desai, A.R., 1969. Rural Sociology in India, Popular Prakashan, Bombay.
6. Doshi.S.L. & Jain.P.C., 1999. Rural Sociology. Rawat Publication, Jaipur & Delh Gowada, S and Others., 1996. Developmental Role of Women members of Panchayati Raj Institutions: A Study in Karnataka, Journal of Rural Development, Vol.15 (2), NIRD, Hyderabad.
7. Imperial Gazetter of India, 1907, The Role of Panchayathraj in New India. Vol-IV-Dhebar U.N.
8. Kaushik Susheela, 2001. Sustainable Politics; Women in Panchayati Raj: Second Round of Elections, Centre for Development Studies and Action, New Delhi
9. Mathew George, 1995. Panchayati Raj:From Legislation to Movement, Concept Publishing, New Delhi,

10. Mathew George, 2002. Panchayathi Raj Institutions and Human Rights in India: International Council on Human Rights Policy.
11. Mayara Shail, 1998. Panchayats and Women : A study of the processes initiated before and after the 73rd Amendment in Rajasthan, Institute of Development Studies, Jaipur, Mimeo.
12. Panchayathi Raj update, Institute of Social Science, Vol.VIII. January-December 2001
13. Parvathamma, 1975. Panchayathi-Raj and Weaker Sections, presented at the seminar held in NIRD, (Unpublished paper), Hyderabad
14. Singh, H.J., 1968. Village leadership, Sterling Publications, New Delhi.
15. Status of Panchayati Raj in the States and Union Territories of India, 2000, Institution of Social Science, New Delhi.
16. Sabyasachi Amitav, 2005. Women's Empowerment in Village Politics.
17. Saxena, N, C., 1999. What is meant by people's participation, A note, Journal of Rural Development.
18. Status of Panchayati Raj in the States and Union territories of India, 2000. Institute of Social Science, New Delhi.